

The Impact of Human Resource Practices on NGOs Organizational Performance with Mediation of Information Technology Capability in Yemen NGOs

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Abstract

Aims and objectives. To examine the degree in which the relationship between human resource management practices and organizational performance improvement are mediated by IT Capability in Yemeni NGOs industry.

Background. Non-governmental Organisations are becoming aware that human resources are an important asset that can provide sustained competitive advantages (Batti, 2013). Successful NGOs recognize the significance of the human element on organizational success and emphasize their development, satisfaction, commitment, and motivation to attain desired objectives.

Design. This quantitative research study used a correlational design. The aim of this study was to understand the relationship between the variables. Therefore, using other quantitative designs such as descriptive, non-experimental, or quasi-experimental would be considered inappropriate.

Methods. The methodology for this research was quantitative. The purpose of this quantitative correlational study was to determine to what extent a relationship exists between HRM Practices and Organisational Performance Improvement. Three quantitative research instruments measured the variables: HRM Practices, Information Technology Capability (ITC), and Organisational Performance Improvement. The quantitative approach “produces results that can be used to describe or note numerical changes in measurable characteristics of a population of interest; generalize to other similar situations; provide explanations of predictions; and explain causal relationship.

Results. The findings of this study show all the variables (Compensation, Recruitment, Training, Employee Participation, Performance Appraisal, and Job Security) predicting Organizational performances are significant. However, most of the relationships with the mediating variable, Information Technology Capability are not supported, except two relationships training (Training> Information Technology Capability) and job security (job Security> Information Technology Capability).

Conclusions. The study concludes that most Yemeni NGO employees lack motivation for their Organizational Performance, regardless their job positions such as senior managers/managers and CEOs/Directors. It is a good indication for Yemen's human capital development, which needs to enhance Human Resource Management Practices factors in the critical areas.

Implications. The Task Technology Fit theory supported this study and Resource-Based View Theory. Combining these theories helped form the conceptual framework that extended the knowledge on Organisational Performance from the Human Resource Management Practices perspective.

Key words: *HRM Practices, Organizational Performance, Performance Appraisal, Yemeni NGO, IT Capability*

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Introduction

NGOs are often described as an intrinsically independent economic factor of a country (Stolfova & Fajfrlikova, 2019). As their label suggests, they are also characterised by being not-for-profit, independent, and different from the business sector (Mayrhofer et al., 2019). NGO independence is important from various perspectives. Politically, independence enables NGOs to counter-balance government and business power and keep them accountable to their own promises and society (Yanacopulos, 2015). NGOs and broader civil society are thus seen by many as contributing to good governance and a democratic regime (Edwards & Hulme, 2015). In conflict situations, independence allows NGOs to undertake critical humanitarian work in politically dangerous contexts (Mowjee, 2016). Economically, independence can foster greater efficiency through organizational differentiation. If NGOs are too close to governments or business then there is little to be gained from using them in service delivery (Mayrhofer et al., 2019).

NGOs are recognized as powerful institutions that could significantly impact the strategy that international aid is gathered and assigned but together on the socio-economic establishments at intervals a country (Ninnes Bert Jenkins et al., 2017). Besides, NGOs are a primary institutional structure for delivering aid. Once touted as a curative, notably among the tutorial literature, NGOs have returned to a lower place, increasing scrutiny for their actions (K. Dupuy, Ron, & Prakash, 2016). Indeed, some have urged that NGOs are a component of the 'new imperialism' that will be a trendy form of domination and exploitation of developing countries. Throughout this context, international influence through political suggests that isn't the only form of management. Instead, multinational institutions and international NGOs can sort 'willing intermediaries' for exerting pressure. Analoui and Samour (2012) suggest that donors, the administrative unit, would possibly themselves be shaped by neo-liberal agendas, even have an associate craving for supporting organizations that promote neo-liberal ideologies like "democratic liberalism and liberal democracy." Such neo-liberal problems, specifically in land, are shown to disempower beneficiaries by giving rise to agonistically logics and practices (Fleig et al., 2015). Kusan (2015) argues that NGOs have given rise to "new publics introduce completely different categories of constituents that minimize sovereignty and challenge states as a result of the alone legitimate actors in international politics" (Dempsey, 2009; Brockington & Scholfield, 2010; and Gleiss, 2014). Many of the sampled local NGOs work with a project orientation focus which means there is a low priority for nurturing human resource capacities and staff retention measures due to the short-term nature of the projects (Yanacopulos, 2015). Some organizations cannot have the right employees at the right time and place (Oelberger, Fechter & McWha-Hermann, 2017).

When they recruit the staff, they face the challenge of retaining them to the end of the project phase as staff leave before the termination of the project (Koddenbrock, 2016). This dynamism experienced in project-oriented organizations is a tremendous challenge as staff turnovers are often high and erratic, destabilizing programming and, eventually, the organization's performance (Carpenter, 2017). Some of the geographical areas where the NGOs operate are inaccessible or remote, and it becomes difficult to attract staff to work in these sites. They are forced to rely on temporary staff or unqualified staff to fill the positions (Walk & Handy, 2020).

Walk & Handy (2020) argued that some of the local NGOs sampled do not have HR guidelines that support staff management. They are not utilized and are instead used as tools to get donor funds sometimes (Khallouk & Robert, 2018). Much of the staffing management issues are done in an Adhoc manner, and it is never clear what the employee is expected to do at a given time (Kerlin, Peng & Cui, 2018). In some organizations, the policies that exist are not aligned with government labor policies. For example, the government has a policy that a nursing mother will be given three months leave with pay, but in some organizations, they either gave one month or the policy was not included (Walk & Handy, 2020). Some NGOs did not have contracts, job descriptions, or letters of appointment for the staff. Therefore, it is difficult to get records of when staff were employed, what they are entitled to, length of the contract, and their responsibilities (Rainhorn, Smailbegovic, & Jiekak, 2010). In some organizations, because they did not have contracts, some of them went without pay during some months, were never given leave breaks from work, were deducted some of their payment for some unexplained expenses by management.

Hence there forth, the effective management and utilization of HRs will probably lead to the performance and sustainability of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) as Sökkie (2013) comments that "the importance of Human Resource Management practices in an NGO as a means of ensuring sustainable growth for an organization cannot be overemphasized, as it is the fundamental strength upon which people; strategies, processes, and operations are based. Therefore, this study will assess human resources management practices' contribution to nongovernmental organizations' performance and sustainability, most specifically in the Yemeni Environment.

A challenge facing most NGOs is how to manage diverse groups that exist in the workforce to ensure they are committed to the organization's mission (Khallouk & Robert, 2018). Many face challenges in the motivation of people of diverse age and gender, and many of the organization still use outdated methods to manage the staff (Oelberger, Fechter, & McWha-Hermann, 2017). For example, there is a rise

in the recruitment of younger, better “educated” teams, which has contributed to tensions between the older “experienced” staff. Therefore, there was a lack of delegation of work clearly and systematically due to conflicting approaches to work and suspicion among the two groups (Brunt, 2016). Sometimes the absence of an educated and skilled labour force within a location affected recruitment as some organizations had to hire part-time staff or work with volunteers (Karkee & Comfort, 2016).

NGOs in Yemen

Nongovernmental organizations have taken on prominent roles in delivering environmental services in Yemen. Various researchers have conducted the work related to the NGOs (Rana, 2012), (Phippard, 2018), (Osman & Mekki, 2017), (Dasgupta, 2017), (Wesarat, Sharif, & Majid, 2017), (Lopez, Smith, & Pagnucco, 2007), (H. Zhou & Pan, 2016) and (Sharma & Bansal, 2017) while others work on related methodologies. Traditionally, the research scholars have examined the performance of NGOs separately and ignored the fundamental indicators that can represent the accurate picture of NGOs and their weighting criteria (Mahat & Pokharel, 2017). They performed a partial view of the study while measuring the NGOs' performance (Wunsch, 2016; Acosta, 2016).

Recently, “the correlations and causalities between different types of human resource management, in NGOs have increased and become more complex (Iizuka, 2018). In Yemen, the continuation of the human resource crisis, and an even more critical part of an NGOs' decision-making in activities, has progressively made unstable than it was previously (Deshkar, 2020). NGOs are strongly associated with human resource management practices due to their dealings with various stakeholders and other factors, including uncertainties (Hartmann, Hartmann, Lopez & Flores, 2020).

The increasing importance and visibility of NGOs have contributed to calls for greater accountability and transparency, with the sources of these demands reflecting the diversity and complexity of the field itself. In some instances, NGOs have adopted metrics imposed by external agents, responding to requirements from governments, foundations, and other donors (DiMaggio & Powell, 2015; Pfeffer & Salancik, 2018). In other cases, NGOs have created their standards for self-regulation, developing voluntary codes of ethics, and establishing umbrella agencies for oversight (Gugerty, 2008; Sidel, 2017). Research in industrialized countries such as the United States indicates that the nonprofit sector has adapted by becoming rationalized and professionalized, meaning that organizations rely more on a credentialed, paid labor force and increasingly develop formal policies and reporting procedures (Abbott, 1988; Hwang & Powell, 2019).

Existing literature shows that none of the researchers combined the relevant and most comprehensive set of related indicators, nor did they use a mathematical linear programming approach to measure NGOs' holistic performance (Brunt, 2016; Karkee & Comfort, 2016; Da Silva, Riana & Soares, 2020). The previous studies' objectives also lack the typical research questions, including the critical assessment of the evaluation index system, evaluation of the weight of NGO performance, and the measurement of weight allocation of NGO evaluation performance for Yemen's case (Delville, 2018; Mathew, 2019, Seddiky, Giggins & Gajendran, 2020).

Organizational Performance

Researchers have different opinions of what performance is. Organizational performance continues to be a contentious issue in management research circles. Javier (2015) equates understanding of the famous 3Es; economy, efficiency, and effectiveness of a specific program or activity. According to Richard et al. (2019), organizational performance encompasses three specific areas of firm outcomes; financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment, etc.), product market performance (sales, market share, etc.), and shareholder return (total shareholder return, economic value-added, etc.).

Organizational performance is the organization's ability to attain its goals using resources effectively and efficiently (Daft, 2017). It can be put organizational performance as the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outcomes: goals and objectives. Understanding should not be confused with productivity; according to Ricardo (2017), productivity is a ratio depicting the volume of work completed in a given amount of time. Performance is a broader indicator that could include productivity and quality, consistency, effectiveness, efficiency, and other factors.

Organizational performance is widely recognized as an important – if not the most important – construct in strategic management research. Researchers also agree that organizational performance is a multidimensional construct. If not the most important, organizational performance is important, complete strategic management research (Rumelt, Schendel, & Teece, 1994). Indeed, the focus on performance differentiates strategic management from other fields (Meyer, 1991); the raising of strategic management research increases understanding of organizational performance determinants and explains how managers can create a superior performance (Meyer, 1991). To advance, therefore, the strategic management field must cumulate knowledge regarding theories that help explain organizational performance and prescribe ways that managers can adjust strategies to improve organizational performance (Combs et al., 2005).

Based on the problem statement above the following research questions are addressed for the study: a. What is the relationship between human resource management practices and IT Capability? b. What is the relationship between IT Capability and organizational performance? c. What is the relationship between human resource management practices and organizational performance? what is the mediating role of IT Capability in the relationship between Human resource management practices and organizational performance?

Figure 1: Research Model

Methodology, design and methods

the focus of this study is the relationship between HRM practices, IT Capability and organisational performance. Therefore, a correlational approach was appropriate for the current study to help identify the level of significance in the relationship between the variables. Using the correlational research allowed the researcher to describe a linear relationship between the variables without affecting each other (Simon, 2010). The researchers’ choice for using a correlational design was based on determining if or to what extent a correlation exists between servant leadership and effective leadership; and servant leadership and ethical leadership, as well as the positive outcomes revealed in prior studies that used the same variables. The sample are NGO employees in Yemen. The reasons for choosing these categories of respondents are; first, they are mostly employees from various organizations at different levels of employment with experience. Secondly, they have been widely used in the prior literature (see for example the work of Ayers & Kaplan, 2005; Behrens, 2015; Brink, A. G., Lowe, D. 1, & Victoravich, 2017; Chiu, 2002; Dalton & Radtke, 2013; Kaplan & Schultz, 2007; Mackey & Deng, 2016) as representatives for employees. In addition, the researcher is of the believe that this target population convincingly is representative of employees who may possibly observe directly or indirectly the types of improper acts relevant to whistle-blowing (Kaplan & Schultz, 2007)

Instrumentation

The essential tool for collecting data in a study that adopts quantitative approach research survey design is questionnaire (Dillman, 2017). This is because it increases the magnitude of confidentiality and allows expression of opinion freely, and hence reduces biases on the side of the researcher as compared with interview and focus group (Salkind, N. J., & Rainwater, 2013). Therefore, this study uses questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. However, researcher has an option to either develop research instrument; to obtain from previous studies and adopt it or to modify the existing one in the past literature in order to make it suitable to the context of the research (Creswell, 2008). For the purpose of this study instruments were adopted from previous academic research. This is because, it has been shown that existing instrument might have been already reliable and validated (Creswell, 2014). The structure of the questionnaire contains different sections. Thus, the first section contains demographic factors of the respondents. The remaining sections of the instrument contain other variables measured on a Seven-point Likert scale. This is because, the selection of 7point likert-scale beside its simplicity, it also enhances the reliability and validity of responses (Dawes, 2008). The use of Likert-Scale with Mid-point can take care of the ambivalent feeling of the respondents. Thus, overcome issues of random error, predictable and systematic biases (Nowlis, Kahn, & Dhar, 2003). The survey used in the current study comprised three instruments to measure the variables. The surveys was distributed to employees at NGOs in Yemen. The researcher will obtaine permission from all authors to use the surveys. The following validated instruments will be used to conduct the research:

Table 1: Sources of the adapted Instruments

Constructs	Survey Items
Recruitment	Onik, M. H., Miraz, M. H., & Kim, C. S. (2018)
Compensation	Balkin and Gomez Mejia 1990
Training	Tabassi, , & Bakar, (2009).
Employee Participation	Bhatti, K. K., & Qureshi, T. M. (2007)
Performance Appraisal	Othman, N. (2014)
Job Security	Pedraza, P., De Bustillo, R. M., & Tijdens, K. (2005).
Information Technology Capability	Aurelio Ravarini, 2010
Organizational Performance	Alegre, J., & Chiva, R. (2008)

Analysis and Findings**Response rate**

Responses	Total
Distributed questionnaires	414
Total Returned	399
Uncompleted questionnaires	09
Response rate	90%
Outlier cases	02
Missing value	04
Total Received Questionnaires for Analysis	384

Age

Table 4.03 shows that the largest percentage was concentrated in categories 25-30, 36-40, 31-35, 46-50, 41-45 and 29-32 years with each of them stood at 26.0%, 21.6%, 19.5%, 14.8%, 12.8%, and 3.9% respectively. This can be explained by the fact that the nature of the work of NGOs requires the natural and logical age for work, which is represented by these six categories. In addition, these categories are more capable of creativity and thinking, as well as the experience of these mentioned categories, which have a significant impact on the organizational performance.

Gender

59.37% of the study sample was males and 40.62% of the sample was females. The researcher attributed this to the nature of the work of NGOs that require more effort, as well as to the males' characteristics which distinguishing them in this area and enabling them to perform their functions better to achieve the organizational performance.

Education Level

Most of the sample of the study is holders of bachelor degrees, whether master, STPM / Foundation / Pre-U Courses and Diploma as the ratio of holders of these certificates to 90.5% of the total sample of the study. There are also 35 PhD / DBA degree holders in the list of respondents. the researcher attributed this to the fact that the nature of the work of the NGO sector imposes on the organization's management in the recruitment process of employees which the job seekers should be acquired a bachelor degree. In general, the participants' education scene has sufficient assortment and the participants' distribution with respect to their education can be viewed as normal.

Job Position

In this study, the sample was a variety of senior management in NGOs of Yemen. The majority of the study sample works in the manager's position 27.30% of the total sample of the study and followed by the top management and executive of the board with 25.50% and 24.2% respectively. Finally, non-executive of the board's position came at the last with 22.4%.

Number of Years of Service in the Current Position

With regard to the number of years of service in the current position, the large proportion was concentrated in the two categories of 6-10 and 11-15 years with 34.2 and 33.5% respectively, followed by the categories of 5 years or less and 16-20 years by 17.7 and 12.7%. The lowest ratio amongst this part is for 21 years and over with 1.8%.

Measurement Model Assessment

The measurement model explains how each construct is measured, and the goodness of fit (Hair et al. 2017) will be used to examine the measures measurement model, as well as reliability and validity issues for all constructs employed in this part.

In social sciences research, there are many causes of measurement error (measurement error is the difference between the actual value of a variable and the value obtained by a measurement), including poorly worded survey questions, misunderstanding of the scaling method, and incorrect application of a statistical approach, which can result in random and/or systematic errors (the error can have a random source, which affects reliability, or a systematic source, which affects validity) (Hair, et al., 2017). All measures in the multivariate analysis very probably include some measurement error. The goal is to decrease measurement error drastically. Multivariate measurement aids researchers in identifying precise measurement error and accounting for it in the study's conclusions. The PLS algorithm results (regression weights) for the whole model are shown in the sections below. Smart PLS 3.0 was used to create the PLS algorithm.

Table 1 shows the indicator loadings, composite reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE), Cronbach's Alpha of the reflective construct in this study. Hair et al, (2016) suggested loading values that equal to or greater than 0.708 will be retained. It indicated a latent variable was able to explain at least 50% of the indicator's variance. All items for Compensation, Recruitment, Training, Employee Participation, Performance Appraisal, Job Security, Information Technology Capability, and Organizational Performance were retained as all the loadings are greater than 0.708. The CR was above the minimum threshold of 0.7 and the AVE was greater than 0.50. Thus, the constructs met the reliability and convergent validity requirement.

Table 1: Summary of Measurement Model Assessment

Construct	Item	Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Recruitment	RE02	0.879	0.926	0.926	0.944	0.771
	RE03	0.878				
	RE06	0.882				
	RE12	0.878				
	RE15	0.873				
Compensation	COM03	0.881	0.954	0.954	0.981	0.731
	COM05	0.814				
	COM06	0.890				
	COM07	0.894				
	COM08	0.876				
	COM09	0.819				
	COM12	0.856				
	COM13	0.830				
	COM14	0.851				
	Training	TRAN02				
TRAN06		0.847				
TRAN08		0.828				
TRAN12		0.848				
TRAN14		0.828				
TRAN15		0.849				
Employee Performance	EMP03	0.803	0.908	0.909	0.932	0.732
	EMP05	0.858				
	EMP06	0.876				
	EMP09	0.854				
	EMP15	0.886				
Performance Appraisal	PA03	0.882	0.923	0.924	0.940	0.722
	PA05	0.815				
	PA09	0.859				
	PA12	0.846				
	PA14	0.849				
	PA15	0.847				
Job Security	JS03	0.855	0.919	0.920	0.937	0.713
	JS05	0.853				
	JS06	0.840				
	JS08	0.814				
	JS12	0.854				
	JS13	0.849				
Information Technology Capability	ITC05	0.839	0.917	0.918	0.938	0.752
	ITC06	0.868				
	ITC09	0.887				
	ITC14	0.862				
	ITC15	0.879				
Organisational Performance	OPI05	0.893	0.923	0.924	0.940	0.722
	OPI09	0.887				
	OPI11	0.865				
	OPI12	0.843				
	OPI13	0.829				

Validity

Three measures were used to check the discriminant validity (the degree to which items differentiate among constructs or measure distinct concepts) of the measurement model: the cross-loadings, Fornell-Larcker criterion, and HTMT. According to (Hair et al., 2017), to evaluate the discriminant validity of the indicators, the first approach is AVE. Moreover, convergent validity is the level to which a measure positively correlates with alternative measures of the same construct. Researchers consider the average variance extracted (AVE) in order to establish convergent validity (Hair et al., 2017).

Table 2: Fornell-Larcker criterion

	COM	EMP	ITC	JS	OPI	PA	RE	TRAN
COM	0.955							
EMP	0.948	0.956						
ITC	0.908	0.893	0.967					
JS	0.928	0.921	0.882	0.944				
OPI	0.922	0.940	0.853	0.916	0.964			
PA	0.952	0.950	0.899	0.924	0.930	0.950		
RE	0.908	0.901	0.872	0.879	0.875	0.924	0.978	
TRAN	0.912	0.916	0.871	0.893	0.911	0.919	0.846	0.837

Direct Hypotheses Testing

Path coefficient was assessed to evaluate the significance of hypothesis tested between the constructs. Based on the model, there were 6 direct relationship results. T-statistic for all paths was generated using SmartPLS bootstrapping in order to

test the level of significance. Running t-statistic on sample size 384 respondents and the direct hypotheses should have brought a result of >1.645, and indicated significant value at 0.05 level. From the Table 4.20 the assessment of the path coefficient, 09 relationships were found to have t-value > 1.645, thus at significant value of 0.05 level.

Table 3: Structural Path Analysis Results

Hypo	Relation	Std. Beta	Std. Error	t-value	P Values	Decision
H1a:	RE -> OP	0.182	0.057	3.187	0.002	Supported
H1b:	COM -> OP	0.064	0.079	2.809	0.000	Supported
H1c:	TRAN -> OP	0.202	0.056	3.579	0.000	Supported
H1d:	EMP -> OP	0.414	0.092	4.482	0.000	Supported
H1e:	PA -> OP	0.178	0.102	1.740	0.008	Supported
H1f:	JS -> OP	0.226	0.054	4.170	0.000	Supported
H2b:	COM -> ITC	0.329	0.093	3.525	0.000	Supported
H2c:	TRAN -> ITC	0.148	0.071	2.093	0.037	Supported
H2d:	EMP -> ITC	0.082	0.101	0.813	0.416	Not Supported
H2e:	PA -> ITC	0.071	0.107	0.660	0.510	Not Supported
H2f:	JS -> ITC	0.144	0.081	1.788	0.074	Not Supported
H3	ITC -> OP	-0.130	0.047	2.779	0.006	Supported

Table 4: Mediating analysis

Hypo	Relationship	Beta	STDEV	T value	P Values	Decision
H4a	RE -> ITC -> OPI	-0.024	0.012	1.926	0.055	Not Supported
H4b	COM -> ITC -> OPI	-0.043	0.021	2.075	0.039	Supported
H4c	TRAN -> ITC -> OPI	-0.019	0.012	1.538	0.125	Not Supported
H4d	EMP -> ITC -> OPI	-0.011	0.015	0.708	0.479	Not Supported
H4e	PA -> ITC -> OPI	-0.009	0.015	0.624	0.015	Supported
H4f	JS -> ITC -> OPI	-0.019	0.013	1.457	0.146	Not Supported

Discussion

The first objective of this study is to examine the relationship between human resource management practices and Managing IT. The study found that only Compensation and Training significantly impact IT Capability. The overall mean score of all other factors has a higher influence on Organisational Performance. This result falls in line with Puwanenthiren (2015) findings that employee's performance objectives can be achieved through the use of appropriate Human Resource Management Practices. It further affirms that Human Resource Management Practices serve as a motivating factor to improve employees' loyalty to organizational goals and targets (Danso et al., 2013). Though none of these authors specified the type of reward system, evidence from this research work identifies compensation as that appropriate reward system that can fine-tune Organisational Performance to the firm's goal and objectives and its related cost. Though compensation has a positive effect on Organisational Performance, it cannot be solely used as a reward system in leather technology industries. This is because profit levels in a manufacturing firm fluctuate depending on the production process. Profit can be meagre at some stages in spite of a high level of Human Resource Management Practices. This can result in relatively lower wages in spite of higher input. As a result, compensation can only be used alongside other

Human Resource Management Practices in NGOs of Yemen.

Moreover, these study findings are also in line with Tippet and Kluvers (2009), where it explored a positive relation between the Compensation and the employee's motivation. On the other hand, Hafiza et al. (2011) opined a positive relationship between extrinsic rewards and employee motivation. The results of the present study indicate that non-financial rewards exert a higher impact on Organisational Performance than financial rewards in the case of NGOs in Yemen. The literature on compensation explains that the Organisational Performance is directly tied to the level of the Organisational Performance. Kotelnikov (2010) refers to this as the level to which employees are motivated in their work depending on how well they can produce in their job. This research concludes that compensation is found to be an integral part of Organisational Performance. Furthermore, the study also suggests that if the NGOs in Yemen are motivated either by financial or non-financial compensation their organisational performance will be multiplied. The second objective of this study is to examine the relationship between IT Capability and organisational performance. The study found that IT Capability has a positive impact on Organisational Performance. It affirms the recommendation that IT Capability should be based on definite, realistic and reliable standards that must be identified and redefined to make greater meaning to the employees (Nyandema et al., 2014). It falls in line with Jesca (2014) assertion that While organizations are investing heavily in IT, some are unsure of the benefits they should derive from IT for increased organizational performance. The empirical evidence shows that IT capability is a phenomenon not well understood within the mine. To simplify this concept, the study had to explore this in terms of the business processes and how information technologies enabled the organization. The study looked at who does what and how they do it within their multiple business units while looking at what the organization does as a business. A. IT Capability Model a) IT infrastructure Byrd and Turner (2017) describe IT infrastructure as the capability to support a diverse range of hardware, software, communications technology, data, core applications, skills and competencies, commitments, and values within the present IT infrastructure's technical and physical base.

The evidence suggests that the organization does not utilize ITCs to their full potential. This has been shown to be accurate, as business units have various systems and the systems operate in silos, while other systems can integrate. System support exists; however, service to all mine sections is hampered by staff shortages. Some functions still run manually, such as contract management. However, IT is utilized

100 per cent throughout the organization for the daily running of all business units. Literature highlights the common knowledge that collaboration in an organization generates information synergy. Information synergy relates to the pooling of resources in a business where persons or business units work together and use IT across roles or subunits (Long & Perumal, 2014).

The findings and literature concur as they show that ITCs align organizations for collaboration and thus produce more information synergy. This means that the systems in various units need to collaborate – rather than run in silos – for the organization to benefit from the value of IT. Greater collaboration produces more information synergy, which influences organizational performance. ITC assists organizational activities and work processes and pools other vital resources (Galagedera, 2019). The study stresses that ITC should be enhanced for the organization to stay competitive and business units to work together using IT across subunits..

The third objective of this study is to examine the relationship between human resource management practices and organisational performance improvement.. The study found that all the factors have significant relationships between Human Resource Management Practices and Organisational Performance. The results are in line with Rewat (2018) findings, where it reveals important empirical results that make a significant contribution to clarifying the question of the role of employee competencies in the relation between HRM practices and organizational performance. Results confirmed H1 by showing that recruitment and selection significantly influence organisational performance. This result parallels the findings of several studies, which found that effective recruitment and selection leads to competitive advantage and high performance of an organization (Chen and Cheng, 2012; Pfeffer, 1994; Storey, 2007). The results validate researchers' assumption (Naquin and Holton, 2006; Lee, 2010). H2 confirms a significant influence of training and development on employee competencies. These results support the contentions of Zumrah et al. (2013) who argue that employees who participated in training apply the new learned skills, knowledge and attitude in their everyday work and demonstrate better abilities and competencies in performing their job. The results are in line with the opinion of researchers (Cheng and Brown, 1998; Swanson, 2001).

Results of H2 and H3 suggest that Compensation and training significantly influence Organisational Performance. This result is consistent with the findings of Ayanda and Sani (2010). They assert that Compensation and training help employees develop such skills, which are important for their

development and growth and are also important for the development and success of the organization as a whole. H4 also has a similar result showing Employee Participants significantly influence organisational performance. This result supports the findings by Osman et al. (2011), who contend that an ineffectual appraisal procedure results in numerous undesirable challenges comprising stalled employee efficiency, less morale, less enthusiasm in supporting organizational values and objectives, consequently delaying the effectiveness of the organization. The results are not in line with the opinion of researchers (Young et al., 1995). These results parallel the findings of several studies that found that employee participation is positively related to employee performance, satisfaction, and productivity (Pfeffer, 1994; Verma, 1995). The results are in line with the opinion of researchers (Ardichvili et al., 2003).

Results of H6 indicate that job security significantly influences organizational performance. According to Geoffrey James, job security has a significant effect on the overall performance of the team as well as on the organization's performance (James, 2012). He noted that organizational with workers with low job security cause people to lose faith in their future, consequently affecting performance. He affirmed that the more an employee enjoys high job security, the more he is likely to effectively perform his task, which is reflected in the organisation's overall performance. For example, tasks are normally broken down in organisations into jobs assigned to each employee. Each of the jobs performed by the employees is assessed through individual performance. This individual performance is part of the overall organizational performance. The employee's individual performance through his job is directly linked with the organisation's overall performance. Therefore, it seems their performance is linked to organizational performance. Their contributions will be more minor and ineffective if they feel low job security in the organization.

For instance, low job security is possible when a particular employees' ethnic group seems to dominate other ethnic groups in some organizations or industries (Bumi, 2011; Hassan, 2010). In this case, the minority employees in that company will feel low job security and, therefore, may not perform effectively. For example, a Chinese owned company may be dominated by more Chinese employees other than other ethnic groups (Bumi, 2011; Hassan, 2010), thereby causing fear of losing their jobs to other minority employee ethnic groups in the company and vice versa. Therefore, employees working in NGOs may feel very low job security and thus, contribute very little to the organization. On the other hand, working in an NGO will also feel low job security, affecting their performance. Based on the different scenarios above, an employee in a company other

than his race may feel low job security. This will affect his/her performance, which is reflected in the organisation's overall performance. Based on this, it can be argued that organizations should find a way of balancing between employee job security and organizational performance as employee job security is a key determinant of organizational performance, especially in a multiethnic environment.

Despite all these, the most recent study conducted by Subramaniam et al. (2011) on the linkage between human resource practices and organizational performance of NGOs in Yemen provided a different result. Although job security was considered as a dimensional or sub variable, it was found that job security is not significantly related to organizational performance. However, the study noted that NGOs seem not to consider job security as a viable strategy because employees tend to give less attention to job security in searching for a job.

The fourth objective of this study is to examine the mediating role of IT Capability in the relationship between Human resource management practices and organisational performance. The findings of this study support that IT capability significantly mediates the relationship between Compensation, Performance Appraisal and Organisational Performance. Several studies are in line with these findings. Most firms under-manage their core software assets (Dutta, 2017). According to Weill and Ross (2019), IT capability is the most important factor in generating business value from IT. They define IT governance as 'specifying the decision rights and accountability framework to encourage desirable behaviour in the use of IT'. Weill and Ross (2017) claim that IT governance is essential because good IT governance pays off; IT is expensive; IT is pervasive; new information technologies bombard enterprises with new business opportunities, firms need to learn about IT value, IT value depends on more than a good technology, senior management has limited bandwidth, and leading enterprises govern IT differently.

It refers that the higher the IT capability of the employees, the higher the employee delivers performance. All in all, this study had identified a significant and robust association between IT capability and Organisational Performance. IT capability has a great influence on performance. In the organization, IT capability reflects an active work orientation in which an employee wishes and feels able to shape his or her work role or context. This feeling of empowerment has been proposed and found to facilitate the commitment of workers in the organization and increase task motivation manifested in four cognitions: meaning, competence, self-determination and impact (Thomas et al., 1990). According to Buckle (2013), IT capability can be a motivational process by which an individual

experiences a sense of enablement and provides an effective buffer against the adverse effects of stress. According to Vardi (2018), IT capability is considered important because of the potential benefits that can result from it, including increased commitment, better decisions, improved quality, more innovation and increased job satisfaction.

Moreover, the findings establish a relationship with performance perceived by employees' managers. This means that the benefits of IT capability are visible for customers and for managers. As supervisors' perceptions are important to provide recognition, promotions and salary increases, it is likely that an empowered workforce will perform better and will remain in the organization longer. Employees' IT capability seems thus to be beneficial to several stakeholders in service organizations: to customers who enjoy the service quality, to employees who can grow faster, and organizations that can secure employees' performance and consequently service quality and organizational success.

Studies have also highlighted the importance of IT capability among frontline employees by granting them autonomy to craft marketing rules and procedures to match customers' needs (Bock et al., 2016), along with training to develop stronger relationships based on benevolence and efforts (Morales, 2005), but none has addressed the role that external stakeholder like customers might play in building employees' IT capability. The findings complement these studies by showing that positive customer feedback represents a context that fosters feelings of IT capability for frontline employees. Future research could combine customer feedback with other IT capabilities to further explore the antecedents of frontline employees' IT capability.

Recommendations for Future Studies

Based on the limitations of the study, future studies are recommended as follows:

To generate achievable policies and talent development strategies with regards to helping the returnees to adapt to the Yemeni working environment, considering the need for more action. It would be interesting if the current integration model between the TRS constructs and Organisational Performance is extended to other predictors, such management practices vary from one organisation to the other. These differences in practices may influence the employees' decisions on Organisational Performance and improve them as human capital assets in Yemen. IT capability predictors would be another construct that could be investigated as a mediator because the current study.

Future research is suggested to be conducted using Roy's Adaptation Model (Roy & Andrew, 2009) to highlight the different perceptions of employees from the working environment. Specifically, it is suggested to conduct research on the four types of Roy's

adaptation model, namely, the physiologic mode, the self-concept mode, the role function mode, and the interdependence mode (Roy & Andrew, 2009), to improvise employees' performance. Moreover, the mediating construct in this study could be further explored as a moderator to evaluate their high and low effect on Organisational Performance.

From the perspective of methodology, it is recommended that the study be extended to use a qualitative approach and an in-depth analysis of benefits, Career growth opportunities, and work-life balance to increase Organisational Performance. Hopefully, this approach would be able to garner in-depth knowledge on the individual experiences of the employees considering the above significant predictors of Employee performance.

Furthermore, there are various avenues for further research in this field. For starters, since Human Resource Management Practices are not one-size-fits-all for every company, it will be fascinating to look into the impact of HRM Practices on service company performance. Employee tasks at service businesses such as banks are more regular, with a lower degree of creativity and innovation. Group work is less likely, and there is a greater degree of specialization and job differentiation. It is critical to do research in this area in order to determine the most relevant HRM strategies for service businesses.

Second, wages and salaries account for a large portion of a company's costs. Human Resource Management Practices are required to produce enticing packages, given that reward is a vital tool that may be used to recruit the ideal person, maintain them, and consistently inspire them to perform at their best. Furthermore, given that the primary goal of any organization is to make a profit, it is critical to investigate the impact of HRM practices on firm profitability. This will aid in achieving a profit-labor cost balance.

Finally, the goal of individual achievement is to help the company succeed. Individual performance is not an algebraic sum of organizational performance. It would be interesting to explore the influence of IT Capability on organizational performance after analyzing the effect of HRM practices on organizational performance.

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